

INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION AND TRANSLATION

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Abstract. *Whoever said that language and communication are key factors in our societal setup was a genius. Vocabulary plays a really important and significant role in the formation of language. Your vocabulary and the changes that come with time are a reflection of your culture and the changes it has undergone over the years. The relationship between language, translation and culture is a key aspect of communication.*

Keywords: *relationship, culture, key, aspect, service*

Translation plays a major role when it comes to understanding the culture or translating any document in the respective culture. For instance, if a translation service in Mumbai, works on a business document for UK client, then the tone, slang and the language have to be according to the UK business culture. This is where the importance of translation in culture comes to the role. Let us look into the definition of what culture, translation and language to know more about the relationship.

· Culture:

Within Nations and in a Nation there are several cultures. How does one define culture? Culture reflects the ways in which people behave. It is a pattern in which we analyse the behaviour, social habits, beliefs, traditions and customs. When we are trying to know more about the culture, language plays an important role and to understand language one needs translations as one might not know of the particular language.

Language:

Language here simply means the tie that keeps cultural significance on a loop. Language can also be classified as the complex system of communication that humans adapt varying from various cultural backgrounds. It makes for the most of the communication system in any culture or we can say every culture.

Translation:

A converting process that helps people who speak different languages to understand each other's perspective and be able to maintain a healthy communication is translation. It again gets down to connecting cultures and eradicating the cultural differences that might exist. The importance of translation in culture and language is high because it pushes the wheel ahead for better communication between two parties.

Upon reading the above three definitions, it is quite evident that culture and translation are related to each other and go hand in hand. The relationship between culture and translation help bridge the gaps that different languages might create. Going back to the fact that we have so many Nations and within a Nation too there are so many languages that are spoken; the translation has been an element of healthy cultural exchange. The interdependent nature of the human race and the need for trade, has given translation a green signal.

What does a good translation do and how it affects cultural exchange?

A good translation gives the reader the same feel that he/she might get while reading a particular text in his/her native language. The importance of translation in culture (<http://blog.bhashabharatiarts.com/translation-plays-an-important-role-in-education/>) is that it

helps to communicate the beliefs and ideas in a proper way which could be understood by people from different literary and cultural backgrounds.

Relationship between Culture and translation:

Translation started so that there is no communication gap between Nation-states and that there can be trade and cultural exchange. The idea was to promote understanding among these Nation-states. Translation as defined by Eugene Nida, an American translation theorist says; translation consists in reproducing the receptor language the closest natural equivalent of the source language, first in terms of meaning and secondly in terms of style. When we talk of keeping the meaning intact and the style at place we imply that it should help a reader is able to connect to the text and understand the references in his own native language. Translation is highly influenced by cultural differences and the accuracy in any translated text is highly proportional to the knowledge the translator has of another culture. This implies that translation not only tests a translator’s linguistic ability, but also how much he/she knows of the target languages’ cultural background.

One cannot overlook the influence that culture has on language and translation. The knowledge of another culture makes it easier for a translator to translate and it keeps the accuracy on a check. The aim of translation is to achieve semantic equivalence and that can only be achieved with a good knowledge of the target language and the source languages cultural backgrounds.

What are Culture universals?

This term might seem new to a lot of people, but culture universals help us enhance communication and couldn’t have been achieved without translations. The exchange of ideas, trade and inter-cultural expansion is due to the concept of culture universals and make up for most of our spiritual and material lives. Culture and translation have a very deeply rooted relationship.

Hiring the right Translation Company:

We cannot overlook the fact that even words and their meaning vary from language to language and to be able to help a person understand another language it is highly important to know the cultural disparities. The fact that culture and translation share a sacred bond is inevitable. This is why hiring professional translation services (<http://www.bhashabharatiarts.com/>) becomes a pressing issue. If you are obliged with the importance of translation in culture, then Bhasha Bharati is the one whom you must connect with.

Every project undertaken is shaped up to give a new dimension to strengthen the relationship. Bhasha Bharati ensures that culture of the specific country is respected while translating documents. So connect with the experts now for promising work.

REFERENCES

1. <http://blog.bhashabharatiarts.com/translation-plays-an-important-role-in-education/>
2. <https://www.bhashabharatiarts.com/>